

Effects of globalization on horn of African countries: Case study of Benadir region; Somalia

DAHIR AHMED HASSAN *

Daha International University, Information technology, Mogadishu, Somalia.

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Abstract

The main focus of this study is to investigate the effect of foreign intervention on domestic politics in Somalia.

Operation Restore Hope of the United States of America was the first foreign intervention to Somalia after the collapsed of Siyad Barre Regime and ensuing chaos and banditry that has engulfed all part of the country and led demolition of all State Institution. Disintegration of the State institutions and law and order has taken place on the same time when the Soviet Union collapsed and Warsaw Pact has disintegrated.

After the collapse of the Siad Barre Regime in 1990's the multilateral military intervention in Somalia was one of the international community's first major attempts to respond to a dangerous new challenge in the post-cold war era--the problem of state collapse and social disintegration. The international community ignored clear warning signs in Somalia and missed several opportunities to use diplomacy to prevent state collapse. As a result, the destruction of the state became more complete and the difficulties in rebuilding a viable system more demanding (Samater, July 1, 1995). The main objective of this study was to investigate the effect of foreign intervention on domestic politics in Somalia a case study south and central in Somalia and the specific objective was

- To examine the methods and types of foreign intervention.
- To investigate the effect of foreign intervention on domestic politics.
- To find out the relationship between foreign intervention and domestic politics in Somalia.

The research design: In this study, an analytical study design was applied. This study design was descriptive cross-sectional study that was be employing because of it is easy to use as the information collect from respondents was not be require to be reinvestigated over a period of time. In a target population of 105, using a Solvent's formula the researcher selected a representative sample size of 84 respondents purposively and simple random sampling. And information was gathered from the respondents by use of questionnaires, and an interview, while the quantitative data was analyzed using SPSS version 20, the qualitative data was analyzed using critical content analysis.

The major findings of the study reveal that, direct and main driving force behind the effect of foreign intervention the respondents a selected, 72.6 % of total of the respondents are selected "military intervention" and 4.8% of total of the respondents are selected "economic intervention", 15.5% of the total respondent are selected "diplomatic intervention" and 7.1% of the total respondent are answered "other". So that most of the respondent are selected "military intervention"

The second findings were 91.7 % (77) of respondents agreed that there was an effect of foreign intervention on Domestic politics, while only 8.3 % (7) showed disagreed that foreign intervention does not have an effect on domestic politics so that most of the respondents agreed there was an effect of foreign intervention on domestic policy.

* Corresponding author: DAHIR AHMED HASSAN

Finally finds was shows 60.7 % (51) agree that there is a relationship between foreign intervention and politics while 39.3% (33) disagree saying there is no relationship between the two variables. So that most of the respondent agreed that there is relationship between foreign interventions on domestic policy.

General Recommendations the researcher Recommend to international community to intervention positive way and also have uniform strategy and common interest lasting solution for Somali's.

Somali problems can be only solved by Somali as they are because they are prime stockholders. And also to stop the military intervention which was made by frontline countries entering into Somalia without authorization of the Somali government and United Nations like Ethiopia in 2006 and many other times as well as Kenyan tropes in 2012. Failure to do this undermines the sovereignty of Somalia as a nation, and their right to live in peace and harmony with the neighboring countries.

Keywords: Globalization; Horn of African; Case Study; Benadir Region; Somalia

1. Introduction

This chapter elaborates the explains how the study Statement of the problem, Purpose of the study Research objectives, Research Questions, Hypotheses, Scope, Significance of study and Operational definitions of key terms during the study.

1.1. Background to the study

Globalization according to Nsibambi, (2001) the Prime Minister of Uganda refers as process of development and increase in interaction among the world's countries and peoples facilitated by progressive technological changes in location, communication, political and military power, knowledge and skills, as well as interfacing of cultural and value systems and practices. In other words, Globalization can be seen as a development which is systematically restructuring interactive phases among nations by breaking down barriers in the areas of culture, commerce, communication and several other fields of endeavor (Ohuabunwa, 1999).

Historically, the process of globalization had started in a small way in the nineteenth century as summit (Devet , 1993) as well as Toyo (2000) records that globalization started when capital moved from Europe to open up new areas in America and Australia, mostly in the building of rail road systems and agriculture that would be central to the expansion of capitalism. The consequent maturation of joint-stock companies and developments in the areas of banking, industrial capital and technology, aided among other things, the mix up for and partitioning of Africa and, its then attendant predatory utilization of these parts of the world.

According to the Ohuabunwa (1999) argues, even though, the pre-eminence of globalization as championed by America was interrupted by the cold war era, with the effective end of the latter in 1990, the west no longer needs to compromise as before, its ideology of globalization culture on the account of communism. The concept of globalization is global and dominant in the world today and It was created by the dominant forces to serve their specific interests. Simultaneously these social forces gave themselves a new ideological name the – “international community”- to go with the idea of globalization (Madunagu, 1999).

In Africa context history is marked by foreign e.g. European involvement and Africa had been in contact with other parts of the world and also had significant interactions within it. Interaction with the outside world particularly Europe and America started way back in the 15th century. This has significantly altered the course of Africa history-culturally, politically, economically etc. In the beginning of the last decade of the 20th century into the 21st century, Africa's linkage with other parts of the world has entered a new phase commonly termed as globalization. Though the term globalization may be new, the substance and ideals are not new to Africa and the world as a whole.

Theories of Globalization can be viewed as interdependence, and that interdependence is again associated with peace and peace increasingly with democracy. People, firms' markets matter most; states matter less, because it is the economy that drives states to make decisions. As the world becomes more interdependent on one another, decisions are made as a collective whole in the economic field, not the independent political state (Ibrahim, 2013).

Consequently, globalization means homogeneity of prices, products, rates of interests, etc. a strong economy under globalization requires transparency, but then that transparency might transfer ideologically to the social and political realms as well. It can be argued that this is exemplified in the latecomers' imitation of the practices and adoption of the institution of the countries that have shown the way. (Ibrahim, 2013).

Another globalization theorist, Robinson focuses on economics as well, but further argues that globalization is the spread of capitalism throughout the world. In his views before globalization was relevant, power was battled in conflicts through militaries and physical strength (Ibrahim, 2013). According to the Giddens (1997) in his work on globalization posited that it is the process of modernization of the world system through the use of institutions. Secondly, he argues that globalization is multifaceted, that it takes place at all levels and sectors of the society.

There are many authors have defined Globalization in different ways according to Akindele (1990) refers to the process of the intensification of economic, political, social and cultural relations across international boundaries. as well as Cerry (1994) also globalization describes the increase of trade and investment due to the falling of barriers and the interdependence of countries.

In the study's Ibrahim (2013) as he extracted from the Globalization Website Globalization describes to the increase of global linkages, the organization of social life on a global scale, and the growth of a global awareness, therefore to the consolidation of world society. Such a definition highlights on much of what the term commonly means, but its meaning is disputed. and It encompasses several large processes; definitions differ in what they emphasize. Globalization is historically complex; definitions vary in the particular driving force they identify. and the meaning of the term is itself a topic in global discussion; it may refer to “real” processes, ideas that justify them, or to a way of thinking about them.

Therefore, in this study Globalization means the process of intensification of economic, political, social and cultural relations across international boundaries aimed at the transcendental homogenization of political and socio-economic theory across the globe. (Ibrahim,2013).

1.2. Statement of the problem

In Africa especially horn African countries faced huge problems of globalization in horn African countries since their position in the international system has been significantly weakened by the fact that it has been losing the race for economic development in general, and human development in particular, to other regions, these poor performances by African countries accounts in part for the political and social instability and rise of authoritarian regimes that have characterized much of postcolonial Africa, further more weakening the ability of African countries to deal effectively with globalization. In Somalia where lacks functional central government and shortage of studies initiates the importance of such study. Thus in order to solve this problem the researcher tries to find out the effect of globalization on horn African Countries.

1.3. Purpose of the study

The Main Aim of this study was to investigate the effect of globalization on horn African Countries especially Somalia.

Objectives of the study

1.3.1. Major objective

The major objective of this study was found out the effect of globalization on horn African Countries Especially benadir region.

1.3.2. Specific objectives

This study attempted to examine the following three specific objectives which are

- To determine the level of globalization, exist on Horn Africa countries
- To Evaluate the ways in which the globalization economic influences on horn African countries.
- To examine the possible strategies of controlling the negative effects of globalization on horn African Countries

1.4. Research questions

- What is the level of globalization on Horn Africa countries?
- How globalization influences on the economies of horn African countries?
- What are the possible strategies of controlling the negative effects of globalization on horn African Countries?

1.5. Scope of the study

1.5.1. Content scope

This study concerned the effect of globalization on horn African Countries and Possible strategies of controlling the negative effects of globalization on Horn African countries.

1.6. Geographical Scope

This study conducted on Horn African Countries and researcher took as Somalia especially Benadir Region as a case study

1.6.1. Time scope

This study conducted time frame from 2016-2017 using cross sectional survey design

1.7. Significance of study

This study is important for the government, community, intellectuals and other researchers who may conduct a study about this title effect Globalization on Horn African countries. as well as This study also help the researchers to fulfill one of the requirements for the award of a Bachelor's Degree of International Relation. Also, it bridges a wide gap that needs to be filled by the present and future researchers or potential researchers. In addition, it contributes information that is useful for decision making on effect of Globalization on African countries as also, was serve as an invaluable source of information that sheds alight attraction the attention of their customers. The Findings and recommendations use by other researchers and scholars as literature.

1.8. Definition of terms

- **Globalization refers** to the process of the intensification of economic, political, social and cultural relations across international boundaries (Akindele, 1990).
- **Horn Africa** means a peninsula of northeastern Africa (the easternmost part of Africa) comprising Somalia and Djibouti and Eritrea and parts of Ethiopia.

2. Literature review

This chapter elaborates the explains the literature review

2.1. Concept globalization

Globalization according to Akindele (1990) refers to the process of the intensification of economic, political, social and cultural relations across international boundaries. Globalization is principally aimed at the transcendental homogenization of political and socio-economic theory across the globe. It is equally aimed at "making global being present worldwide at the world stage or global arena" (Fafowora, 1998). In other words, as Ohuabunwa, (1999) once opined: Globalization can be seen as an evolution which is systematically restructuring interactive phases among nations by breaking down barriers in the areas of culture, commerce, communication and several other fields of endeavor. just put, globalization is the term used to describe the changes in societies and the world economy that result From dramatically increased international trade and cultural exchange. Cerry (1994) also said, globalization Describes the increase of trade and investment due to the falling of barriers and the interdependence of countries.

In specific economic contexts, the term refers almost exclusively to the effects of trade, particularly trade liberalization or "free trade." Banjo (2000), insisted that the process of globalization is impelled by the series of cumulative and conjectural crisis in the international division of labour and global distribution of economic and political power, in global finance and the functioning of national states.

The concept of globalization is global and dominant in the world today. It was created by the dominant forces to serve their specific interests. Simultaneously these social forces gave themselves a new ideological name the –"international community" - to go with the idea of globalization (Madunagu, 1999). Globalization has turned the world into a big village. in spite of the ambiguities of the concept, the important nature of globalization is the compression of space and time, as a result, the world becomes one, and interactions among diverse people begin to look like those within a village. Thus terms such as "one world" and "villagization.

In its contemporary form, globalization is driven by variety of forces. These, Colle (2000) argued are flow of financial and economic resources with particular reference to the flow of goods and services and, to a large extent, labour, technology, transport, communications and information technology, the spread of culture from one corner of the world to the other, and global diffusion of religious ideas as well as ideologies.

2.2. The effect of globalization on africans

According to Nsibambi (2001) argues that the effect of globalization on the State in Africa is not only of an economic nature. The process and the outcome of globalization involve a lot more than economics. Globalization includes permeation of political ideas and practices across borders. It includes permeation of cultural and religious beliefs and practices, resulting in dilution of some cultures. It includes the permeation of administrative/managerial concepts and practices across borders and organizations. It includes the domination by some super-powers through military coercive means and the impositions that go with it. It involves internationalization of conflicts that would otherwise remain local.

As well as in the study Ibrahim (2013) suggested that In Africa, its position in the international system has been considerably weakened by the fact that it has been losing the race for economic development in general, and human development in particular, to other regions, these poor performances by African countries accounts in part for the political and social instability and rise of authoritarian regimes that have characterized much of postcolonial Africa, further weakening the ability of African countries to deal effectively with globalization. This does not in any way mean that globalization was be discussed on the two sides: positive and negative impacts.

2.3. The negative impacts of globalization on Africa

It is important to note, optimistically, that globalization offers great opportunities. However, it is probably more important to be clear about the negative aspects of globalization and the fact that its benefits are very unevenly shared and its costs are unevenly distributed among, across and within countries. This is very true especially when seen in the light of African countries. Both in concept and in practice, for every positive aspect of globalization, there is negative side: "While globalization has positive, innovative, dynamic aspects, it also has negative, disruptive, marginalizing aspects" (UNDP Human Development Report 1999, page 25).

According to the Tendon (1998) states that the cold war which was born out of the process for globalization has had significant consequences for Africa. During its height in the 1960's and 1970's, the cold war witnessed the emergence of authoritarian regimes in the form of one-party or military regimes. This was largely result of the support of the two blocks to keep African countries in their respective camps. This has in turn significantly reduced Africa's international negotiating power and its ability to maneuver in the international system. In sum then, the cold war and its demise have worked against democracy and economic development in Africa.

as well as Oyejide (1998) found out the Specific impact of globalization on Africa were identified were in the political sphere, the most significant outcome is the erosion of sovereignty, especially on economic and financial matters, as a result of the imposition of models, strategies and policies of development on African countries by the International Monetary Fund, the World Bank and the World Trade Organization.

Economically, globalization has, on the whole, reinforced the economic marginalization of African Economies and their dependence on a few primary goods for which demand and prices are externally Determined. This has, in turn accentuated poverty and economic inequality as well as the ability of the vast number of Africans to participate meaningfully in the social and political life of their countries.

As well as the negative effect of globalization is the cultural domination from outside that goes with globalization, African countries are rapidly losing their cultural identity and therefore their ability to interact with other cultures on an equal and autonomous basis, borrowing from other cultures only those aspects that meet its requirements and needs. (Ibrahim 2013).

Furthermore Ibrahim (2013) suggested that Globalization on the whole impacts negatively on the development and consolidation of democratic governance. One form of this is the reduction of the capacity of governments to determine and control events in their countries, and thus their accountability and responsiveness to their people, given the fact that the context, institutions and processes by which these decisions are taken are far from democratic.

In addition, that Globalization introduces anti-developmentalism by declaring the state irrelevant or marginal to the developmental effort. Development strategies and policies that focus on stabilization and privatization, rather than growth, development and poverty eradication, are pushed by external donors, leading to greater poverty and inequality

and undermining the ability of the people to participate effectively in the political and social processes in their countries. Welfare and other programs intended to meet the basic needs of the majority of the population are transferred from governments to non-governmental organizations that begin to replace governments making them to lose the little authority and legitimacy they have.

Finally, by imposing economic specialization based on the needs and interests of external forces and transforming the economies of African countries into series of enslaved economies linked to the outside but with very little linkages among them, Democracy, with its emphasis on tolerance and compromise, can hardly thrive such an environment (Rodrik 1994).

Further, Mule (2000) views that the economic specialization imposed on African countries makes rapid and sustainable growth and development impossible, conflicts over the distribution of the limited gains realized from globalization becomes more acute and politicized. Vulnerable groups, such as women, the youth, and rural inhabitants, fare very badly in this contest and are discriminated against. This further erodes the national ethos of solidarity and reciprocity that are essential to successful democracies. Finally, Globalization, by insisting on African countries opening their economies to foreign goods and entrepreneurs, limits the ability of African governments to take proactive and conscious measures to facilitate the emergence of an indigenous entrepreneurial class. (Mowlana 1998).

2.4. Positive impact of globalization on Africa

According to the Ibrahim (2013) Highlights the following main positive impact of globalization on Africa and there are

- Globalization has eased international trade and commerce, facilitated foreign investment and the flow of capital while called for greater accountability and responsiveness of leaders to their people, globalization has often pressed African leaders to adopt policies and measures that are diametrically opposed to the feelings and sentiments of vast majority of their people.
- By defining basic and generally accepted principles of democratic governance, such as good governance, transparency and accountability, in narrow terms, conditioned by particular historical, political, social, and cultural factors, while leaving little or no room for adapting them to different societies and cultures.
- There are international lobby and pressure groups in various fields. There are universities and institutions of higher learning with all their power to impact knowledge, skills and attitudes that shift behaviors of societies and state leadership as well as followership. All these combines to reinforce the phenomenon of globalization and force the state to shift its behavior and the way it relates with both its “subjects” and its internal and external partners.
- Globalization opens people’s lives to other cultures and all their creativity and to the flow of ideas and values. Information and communication technologies have eased interaction among countries and peoples. It is creating a global village out of a wide and diverse world. One major positive impact of globalization on Africa is that it has made available information on how other countries are governed and the freedoms and rights their people enjoy. It has also opened African countries to intense external scrutiny and exercised pressure for greater transparency, openness and accountability in Africa.

2.5. Possible strategies of controlling the negative effects of globalization on Africa

Having studied the advantages and disadvantages of globalization it becomes obvious that strong African countries are in a better position to fend off these negative consequences and may even see their democracies, economy and military strengthened. Below are the strategies of that when adapted was bring the expected merits:

2.5.1. The overstretched capacity to regulate and protect the environment

The capacity of most African States to handle issues such as production of harmful chemicals, global warming, epletion of natural resources destruction of organic agriculture, dumping of nuclear waste is still limited. However, as global actors invest and expand their activities, especially related to industrial, agricultural, mining, forest exploitation and fishing, the regulatory capacity of public administration in African countries, which is already limited in many respects is becoming overstretched. (Ibrahim,2013).

2.5.2. Improve and not undermining the power of the African State

According to Ibrahim, (2013) Argues Most African governments are finding themselves in a situation of “fait accompli” when it comes to making certain policies and decisions. International agencies such as the World Bank, IMF, United Nations, World Trade Organizations, etc. take decisions which are binding on African countries. This could be looked at as eroding the sovereignty and power of the State.

2.5.3. Improve the democratization process

There is an ongoing democratization struggle in Africa. Some African countries began the process of democratizing their governments, political systems and societies sometime back. However, the international partners they are working with in this globalized world are hardly democratic. While the democratization process would require that the people of the country in question get involved in the taking of decisions and policies that concern them, some of the big decisions affecting Africa today are more or less imposed by the globalization players such as the World Bank, IMF, the World Trade Organisation, etc. (Ibrahim, 2013).

2.5.4. Improve the overstretched capacity to handle international and computer-based crime

According to Ibrahim, (2013) suggested that The African State and its forces of law and order were used to handle "traditional crimes". However, with globalization there has been an increase in crimes (drugs, pornography, international corruption etc.) that had been at lower magnitude. In addition, progress in information technology has facilitated the emergence and growth of computer-based crimes, especially fraud. For this the law enforcement agencies have not been well prepared. The increase in these crimes across borders makes the force of law and order look helpless, unhelpful and incapable.

2.5.5. Making the task of poverty eradication more indigenous

As global actors pressurize African governments to open up more and more to maximize foreign investments and capital inflows, and as big multinationals and local enterprises utilize this environment to cater for their interests, the government is having less and less room to pay attention to the abject poverty amongst the poor and rich both in and between countries. The African State was had to be encouraged to pay more attention to the fate of its poor populace than to the fate of big global actors. The big global actors can talk for themselves with little problem. The issue is: who was talk for the poor? (Ibrahim, 2013).

2.5.6. Avoid Debt accumulation and the debt burden

The phenomenal debt burden of African countries is well known. Most of the accumulation of this debt over time was as much a result of the incapacity of the borrowers to pay back as it was of the ease with which the lenders gave money to the countries. This was, and still is, facilitated by the context of globalization.

2.5.7. Control Drain on the human capacity of the State

Globalization has opened borders and relatively freed labor movements. But for African countries this has aggravated the problem of brain drain, which has existed for a long time. Although most African countries with appropriate financial policies receive remittances from their nationals working abroad, it is not clear whether the contribution of some of the most qualified to the process of developing their countries would not be more than the remittances they send back home from "exile". It is noted, however, that this problem should not be over simplified. (Ibrahim, 2013).

2.5.8. Indigenization of public expectations and social demands

The interaction between local sociopolitical- economic forces and global actors has generated new and or different demands from African societies and this has increased pressure on the public administration system to re-adjust to these demands constantly. Examples of such demands include: the demand for transparency and accountability, democracy, a clean environment, gender equality, human rights and freedoms, poverty eradication, competent leadership, effective service delivery and applying New Public Management approaches in public administration. These demands require that public administration systems and practices accordingly re-adjust consistently. In most cases, these demands are expressed by the private sector and civil society both national and international, without considering the cost of what it would take to meet them. This is often beyond the capacities of African states. Moreover, some of the demands from international circles are not in line with the contextual realities in Africa. (Ibrahim, 2013).

2.5.9. Economic Development Paradigms, Models, Strategies and Policies

As has already been made clear, development strategies and policies followed by African countries are increasingly those formulated by outsiders, which are then uncritically imposed on African countries as condition for aid, investments, trade access, and political and military support. Not surprisingly, these strategies and policies serve more the interests of external forces rather than those of the African people they claim to be assisting.

2.5.10. Action at the level of citizens and civil society

It is evident that the most important resource of any country is its citizens. African leaders should therefore concentrate their efforts on educating their people, sensitizing and educating them on their civic, social, economic and cultural rights and responsibilities, and empowering them so that they could defend their rights and interests while contributing fully to the overall development of their countries.

2.6. Impact on globalization in Somalia

Somalia's communities have had to deal with a period of statelessness for longer than any other society in the contemporary world. Somalia also ranks among the lowest countries in the world on UNDP's Human Development Index (HDI). It might, therefore, seem reasonable to view Somalia as a country left out of the loop of new global markets, technologies, politics and cultures. In reality, however, Somalia has had a complex and uneven set of interactions with global actors and trends. This paper examines the impacts of globalization on Somalia. We see globalization as the extension of trends and influences (such as ideas, concepts, knowledge, ethics and technology as well as behaviors) across erstwhile barriers (ethnic, linguistic, cultural, religious, political or environmental). It must be emphasized that globalization is not merely a homogenizing and integrating force, but divides and fragments societies as well. Globalization creates differences.

The unevenness of the process is creating inequalities within nations, regions, and communities; disparity and insecurity of incomes; rapid transmission of financial and political crises between different areas of the planet; the spread of crime, health threats and environmental degradation on a previously unknown scale. People are affected differently by globalization, and they react in a variety of ways. Groups vary in the permeability of their boundaries, allowing some trends to filter through, while others are firmly rejected. Somalia illustrates dramatically the complexity of this transformation, the choices societies can make in the adoption or rejection of trends or behaviors, and the interesting ways in which 'directives' from well-off global partners are interpreted and used for local benefit.

Whereas the collapse of the Somali State (and the ensuing civil war) has causes (and hopefully solutions), that are profoundly endogenous, it can be said to be in some ways a consequence of globalization (especially the end of the cold war), it is also true that the process of globalization in Somalia was enhanced by the collapse of the State. Because the former Somali State had been of the "command and control" type, its persistence would have meant greater opposition to the penetration of trends and ideas than its disappearance.

Although the jargon associated with globalization is new, the process is ancient. The Horn of Africa has been affected, on and off, for almost 4000 years. The Ancient Egyptians imported frankincense from Somalia, which they called the "Land of Punt". It was known to Rome as the "Regio Aromatifera" or "Regio Cinnamomifera". It was a center for trade by the Phoenicians, Greeks, Indians and other East Asians. As a commercial center it went into decline with the Christian era, although it was used as a refuge by Muslims to escape persecution before Islam became widespread in the Arab countries. In the latter half of the second millennium Turks, Portuguese and Egyptians visited the coastal areas. The interior was periodically invaded by Ethiopian forces. At the end of the nineteenth century, the area was partitioned between the European colonial powers, Britain, France and Italy, as well as Ethiopia.

In Somalia, and elsewhere, 'global' interactions have, until now, been limited and sporadic. At the end of the 20th century, however, globalization has become a dominant force with distinctive features that include technologies that have dramatic effects on time and space, and the interconnection of people in ways that are more immediate than ever before.

In order to understand the impact of this new era of globalization on Somalia, it is necessary to look at three different areas of Somali society: its political history, the diversity of its social groups, and its economy. In each area, the civil war has added another dimension to the set of interactions.

It is important to understand that globalization has had direct effects on Somalia (colonialism, foreign aid, imposed ideologies, telecommunications, the spread of new cultures), and indirect effects, the most dramatic of which has been the civil war which has caused acute internal conflicts, and widespread international concern.

Globalization and the political process. For a period of 21 years, Somalia existed under the authoritarian regime of Mohamed Siyad Barre, whose adoption of "scientific socialism" ("Hawliyo Hantiwadaag") led to the imposition of a Statist economy. Somalia's low rate of urbanization and the small number of foreigners in the country at the time accounted for the low level of exposure to the more obvious global trends. The lack of outside influences was maintained by restrictions on the importation of foreign books and periodicals. Although viewed as a society in isolation, Somalia's

geographically strategic location in the Horn of Africa meant that, between 1960 and 1990, it attracted one of the highest amounts of per capita foreign aid in the world. The effects on the expansion of the civil service, military build up, industrial development and patronage and corruption in the financial sector are difficult to overstate. In the mid 1970s, Somalia had one of Africa's largest standing armies, and spent from 40% to 50% of its budget on defense and security. External donors underwrote nearly all of the human development activities and services. In some cases, the accomplishments have a positive aspect: a thriving export market in livestock and bananas and cereal production, though even these activities enjoyed the benign neglect of the Somali State, rather than its enthusiastic support (especially in the case of livestock). Unfortunately, the State never came close to sustaining itself on locally generated revenues.

Globalization resulted in the détente between the East and the West. Somalia's strategic importance was based on East/West competition in the Horn of Africa. But Siyad Barre was oblivious to the changing international situation, and the possibility that Somalia's loss of strategic importance would soon be followed by a decline in military aid. The withdrawal of support by the USSR during the Ogaden war was followed by the provision of aid from the US. The amounts provided by the Americans were substantially lower, as they had never considered Somalia as strategically placed as Ethiopia. A series of insurrections began to plague the country, and in 1988 Siyad Barre's brutal attack on Hargeisa led to charges of genocide, and the subsequent freezing of aid from the West. Within two years the regime collapsed, the end of the Somali State came shortly after, followed by a civil war. Siyad Barre's regime and its manipulative relationship with global partners on opposite ends of the political spectrum left a dangerous legacy. The massive amounts of weaponry provided by its former patrons contributed to the violent warfare and banditry experienced in 1991-1992. Siyad Barre's previous manipulation of clans had created an atmosphere rife with inter-clan mistrust and hostility.

The abuse of power and repression suffered by the Somali people left a deep distrust of any central government. Finally, the high levels of corruption and personal wealth amassed during the days of massive foreign aid donations continue to fuel the fixation that Somali faction leaders have with foreign assistance. To this end, Somali leaders still believe that if they can create some sort of internationally recognized state, or political structure, international funding was resume on a grand scale.

The UN intervention in Somalia from 1992 to 1995 resulted in a new influx of foreigners, their values and their money, and a new and rapid phase in its globalization. Somalis who had cultivated contempt for the Western languages suddenly found them useful in acquiring well-paying jobs. Foreign products (sodas, computers and other items) which had, until then, been prohibitively expensive (or simply prohibited) made an appearance. Losing one's life over inter-clan became less tolerable, as many Somalis realized that a different way of life existed, and might even be within their reach.

Somalis came up with a number of ingenious strategies to please donors, while at the same time getting access to the resources available. During the period from 1960 to 1969, Somalia had experimented with multi-party democracy. After that, it entered a period of nationalism and repression, together with the prohibition of local NGOs and political parties. The international presence in Somalia after 1992 was looking for political movements of one sort or another. Somalis responded by establishing factional organizations, then a number of local NGOs, and then systems of representation by elders (whose traditional influence had been, tour a tour, undermined and enhanced under Siyad Barre). Although these groupings have roots in the indigenous cultures of the region, it is clear that most of them reflected the desire to obtain a share of foreign aid, using paradigms and structures acceptable to the international community. For example, most of the many local NGOs that emerged during this era were known as 'pocket NGOs'. They were simply fronts for factions or businesses formed to secure grants and contracts from international agencies, which had been encouraged to work through 'local counterparts'. When aid began to dry up in 1995, these NGOs disappeared. Those that remain now tend to be authentic, and was perform useful service, provided that they are able to maintain their independence from clans and factions.

Another method used by the UN to revive the government in Somalia was an attempt to establish district councils in the country, which could serve as local authorities, and as interlocutors between local communities and aid agencies. In some cases, these creations have been successful, but in many instances they ceased to exist after UNOSOM's departure.

A current trend in globalization is a shift in political culture from unity and nationalism to the concept of regionalism, decentralization and local governance. Interestingly enough, the Somali leaders at the forefront of this shift towards regionalism (Abdirahman Tuur, Mohamed Ibrahim Egal, Abdullahi Yussuf) are political veterans of nationalism (or chauvinism, in the eyes of some). They were, however, able to take up this new point of view, and Egal and Yussuf are now ruling regions of the former Somalia. These leaders were able to see the trend towards decentralization and local

governance, and that a commitment to these principles is accepted (encouraged, in fact) by international bodies. It should not be assumed that these Somali leaders have given up their national ambitions.

They have, however, decided to use this tactic in order to build political entities, which, just a few years ago, they would have found unthinkable. One symptom of globalization is a retreat of sovereignty in a market-driven global environment. Sovereignty operates in the context of political solutions to problems, but the market imposes economic realities that often assume primacy over national laws and the wishes of the citizens. In this case, national laws (if they exist), become invalid, or are overridden by multinational business interests. An example of this was the proposed Multilateral Agreement on Investment (MAI) that would have given investors rights to compensation by governments if their actions (for example, to protect their workers or the environment) undermine investors' ability to reap profits. In a global counter-effort, an array of international groups were able to stop this particular measure, but the World Trade Organization has provisions that are equally worrying, in this case for Somalia (see section on Environment and Economy). The MAI and WTO issues fall within the realm of legal business interests. However, illegal international commercial activities often involve exploitation of resources, or other activities within the boundaries of other countries that are ignored unless international force is brought to bear on the culprits. One example of this, which has affected Somalia, is illegal fishing within territorial waters (although it is possible that some of the fishing companies had received permits from faction leaders). Another is the dumping of toxic wastes along the Somali coast, possibly by Swiss and Italian firms who specialize in this business. The countries involved in dumping and illegal fishing are reported to include Italy, Russia, Ukraine, Spain, Portugal, Romania, South Korea, Taiwan, Thailand, Pakistan, India and Kenya. Ironically, the combination of illegal dumping and fishing can pose health hazards to consumers in other countries, as there is no regulation of either activity. In the end, it might be Somalia's fishing industry whose reputation is damaged if the fish stocks are contaminated by toxic or nuclear waste.

Somalia's lack of a 'legitimate' government in the worldview aggravates this situation. The response to illegal activities is ineffective and weak, the country lacks representation in various world bodies, is thus unable to plead its case, and must rely on an international network of interested individuals and organizations to bring the matter to the world's attention. The situation with Somalia's landmines and unexploded ordnance is especially serious. Somalia receives comparatively little money for de-mining, although Puntland and Somaliland have publicly endorsed the Landmines Treaty, which they have not been permitted to sign. As a result, the commitment of both regions to abolishing landmines is not recognized.

Another threat to sovereignty is the printing of banknotes. Since 1991 there have been a number of attempts by factional leaders to print new banknotes, with which they could fund their rise in power and influence. Somali currency was printed, especially during UNOSOM's presence, but traders were usually aware of its existence, and the amounts printed were never enough to cause major concern. In 1994, Somalia started printing and issuing its own currency, the Somaliland Shilling (SlSh).

In 1996, Mohamed Farah Aydiid struck a deal with a Canadian printing company and a Malaysian intermediary for a massive number (165 million) of new banknotes. He received the first consignment, and used this to maintain the strength of his alliance. More recently, his son, Hussein, tried to do the same. He was less successful as he had to be satisfied with what the Air businessmen were waging to part with – another symptom of globalization, with sovereignty held at bay and the upper hand held by economic forces rather than the clan, or superior weaponry. Other faction leaders have plans to print banknotes, and if they succeed, the Somali currency may soon collapse.

Privatizing the national currency in this way can eventually have serious negative impacts on the economy, especially if it means dollarization. At present, there is complete freedom of the foreign exchange market, the Somali shilling rules between Kenya and the Horn, with only a small part of the Northwest region using the SlSh. Therefore, apart from this area, there is a common market, and monetary union. If the Somali shilling is destroyed, there may be a delay before the dollar takes over. On the other hand, a new currency may be introduced. Replacement of the national currency with dollars, or a new currency was, therefore, have a negative impact on business (by destroying the unity of the market and raising the cost of transactions), and on the poorest sections of the Somali population (due to inflation first, and the indivisibility of the US dollar in the country). There are also political costs to creating a new monetary union, which can hardly be afforded at this time.

Globalization's weakening of sovereignty enters the political realm when international bodies put pressure on governments to curb abuses of human rights (such as UN attempts at humanitarian interventions by international coalitions). This has, to some extent, taken on the characteristics of a North/South confrontation. The North argues that it has a duty to intervene in the case of war crimes, or crimes against humanity. Countries in the South tend to see this as a form of neo-colonialism, or interference in internal affairs. They also argue that this pressure is not applied

consistently. When criticized on the treatment of their citizens, many Southern countries tend to adopt a more absolutist view of national sovereignty. (Somalia watches 2000)

2.7. Concept of horn of Africa

The term “Horn of Africa” is not only a geographical expression; it is rather ageopolitical concept. Its extent is therefore fluid and depends on the geopolitics of the region. The proper Horn of Africa consists of Ethiopia, Eritrea, Djibouti, Somalia, the Sudan, and South Sudan. Stretchily, it sometimes also encompasses Kenya and Uganda (“Greater Horn”). In its international relations and diplomatic interactions, the Horn of Africa has established close ties with the Middle East, particularly with Egypt and Yemen. For this particular article, the Horn of Africa refers to Ethiopia, Eritrea, Djibouti, Somalia, the Sudan, and South Sudan. (Alemu, 2014). By 2008, the population of the “Greater” Horn of Africa was more than 213 million. On average of 79% of the population of the region is engaged in agriculture and 21% in the industry (World Bank, 2009). The Horn proper (Ethiopia, Eritrea, Djibouti, Somalia and the Sudan and the South Sudan) is the home of over 176 million people of diversified ethnic composition and religion. The Horn is the least developed and stable region of the world. The region witnessed internal conflicts in Somalia, the Sudan, Kenya; inter-state war between Ethiopia and Eritrea; cross-border armed group movement in Djibouti and food insecurity in almost all the countries (Getachew, 2009).

3. Research methodology

This Part was discussing the strategy and methodology of the study, in this part the researcher was introduce research design, research population which includes sample size and sampling procedure, the research data gathering procedure, data analysis and interpretation ethical consideration, and finally limitations of the study.

3.1. Research design

According to Parahoo (1997) defines a research design as a plan that describes how, when and where data are to be collected and analyzed. while Polit et al (2001) describe a research design as the researcher’s overall for answering the research question or testing the research hypothesis. As Mentioned above, the main Aim of this Study is to examining the effect of globalization on horn African Countries and Possible strategies of controlling the negative effects of globalization on Horn African countries case study benadir region somalia in order to attain the objectives of this study the researcher was adapt Quantitative research design which relies on numerical data.

Particularly this study used descriptive cross-sectional design that was employed because of it is easy to use as the information collect from respondents was not be require to be reinvestigated over a period of time.

3.2. Study area and population

Population as “the total number of units from which data can be collected”, such as individuals, artifacts, events or organizations. (Parahoo, 1997), Similarly Oso and Onen, (2008) target population refers to the whole numbers of subjects or the total surroundings of interest to the researcher and finally Burns and Grove (2003) define population as all the elements that meet the criteria for inclusion in a study.

Thus, the researcher conducted this study in horn African countries especially Mogadishu, and the number of the target population is 105 respondents.

3.3. Sample size and sampling techniques

The study was focus on horn African countries especially Mogadishu and was take sample size 84 respondents in order to select this sample the researcher was use non-probability and purposive sampling. As Mentioned Parahoo (1997) in non-probability sampling researcher’s use their judgment to select the subjects to be included in the study based on their knowledge of the phenomenon. and Purposive sampling defined as a method of sampling where the researcher intentionally chooses who to include in the study based on their ability to provide necessary data. (Parahoo 1997). The justification for choosing this approach is that the researcher seeking knowledge about the effect of globalization on horn African Countries and Possible strategies of controlling the negative effects of globalization on Horn African countries case study benadir region somalia The sample size constituted 84 respondents drawn from the categories of respondents in the study area and population. The solvent’s formula was to determine the minimum sample size.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Na^2}$$

$$n = \frac{105}{1 + 105(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{105}{1 + 105(0.0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{105}{1} \cdot 25$$

$$n = 84$$

- Where n = sample size
- N target population
- a = 0.05 coefficient of validity

3.4. Data collection methods

According to the Oso and Oneen , (2008) refers Data collection as the accumulation of specific evidence that was enable the researcher to properly analyze the results of all activities by using research design and procedures. Thus, after research design has been defined the task of data collection starts and the methods of data collection was used for this study were primary and secondary data.

The primary data are those data which are gathered afresh and for the first time, and hence happen to be original in character. While the secondary data, on the other hand, are those data which have already been collected by someone else and which have already been passed through the statistical process. (Oso and Oneen , 2008) . Secondary data was retrieved from books, journals articles related the effect of globalization on horn African Countries and Possible strategies of controlling the negative effects of globalization on Horn African countries case study benadir region Somalia , while primary data of this study was collected through the instrument of Questionnaire.

Instrument of Questionnaire is a tool for data collection method which carefully designed in accordance with the specification of research questions and hypothesis. Instrument of Questionnaire may also be defined as a self-report instrument used for gathering information about variables of interest in an investigation. (ABAE, ECON, and Wilberforce, Nd). A questionnaire is often a onetime data-gathering mechanism on the variables of interest to the researcher. The researcher developed by Questionnaire and the total items of the questionnaire.

The main reasons that the researcher select a Questionnaire as data collection method are because the instrument of Questionnaire is less expensive compared to other methods, and Questionnaires present greater assurance of anonymity. finally, Questionnaire helpful when we are trying to collect information from large numbers of people. because the researchers examining the effect of globalization on horn African Countries and Possible strategies of controlling the negative effects of globalization on Horn African countries case study benadir region somalia . and reliability of the questionnaire was test by using pilot study.

3.5. Data analysis

Once the researcher completes data collection it was go to the analyzing stage and the researcher used Descriptive statistics was include those of the mean and standard deviation of responses among respondents. Data presentation was due by using of frequency tables. In order to ensure that the gathering information is clearly understood. Item analysis was conducted to find out the internal consistency and reliability of each individual item.

Cronbach's Alpha test was also used to test internal reliability. All these analyses were conduct by using statistical software program, SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences).

In the questionnaire each selected one to four scale for where, 1=strongly disagree, 2=disagree; 3=Neutral 4=agree; 5=strongly agree.

The following table including the mean range, respondent mode and descriptions

The interval can be calculated as following = (5-1)/5 = 0.8

- 1.00-1.80 strongly disagree --very poor
- 1.80-2.60 disagree-----poor
- 2.60-3.40 neutral----- Fair
- 3.40-4.20 agree ----- very good
- 4.20-5.00 strongly agree-----Excellent

3.6. Ethical considerations

To conduct this study, the researcher was behaved ethically and confidentially, thus, the researchers was keeping any confidentiality of data and was be exclusively use for the purpose academic and as the respondents were informed about of the contents and the aims of the research prior to administering of any instrument.

3.7. Limitation of the study

- Shortage of the time for doing such research
- Insecurity conditions stopped a lot of times the researcher to reach the location of research Centre
- Security might be challenge since the environment of the research is completely hostile
- With the availability of all these challenges, the researcher was spare no force to complete this significance study as part of the degree’s requirement as well as the taking consideration the societal benefits of this study for the whole Somali community.
- The cost of the questionnaire and tools were very expensive because you need to print a lot of questionnaire letters.

4. Data presentation and analysis

This chapter presents the data analysis and Discussions of the study findings and it was mainly focus on the Demographic data of the respondents in terms of Gender, Age, marital status, education and occupation under the general questions.

The presentation, interpretation and analysis of the data collected were in accordance with the main purpose of the study the *Effect of globalization on horn African countries*. The presentation and analysis of data was be based on research objectives and questions.

The study design was Descriptive design and quantitative data was collected through questionnaires. After collection data was analyzed by using SPSS program and the results was presented as text, frequency table.

4.1. Demographic data

This study was conducted in Somalia particularly in district of Mogadishu; the data was collected from 84 respondents. This section was presented the demographic information of the respondents by beginning with the gender of the respondents, their Ages, marital status and level of education.

Table 1 Age of Respondents

Age of Respondents			
		Frequency	Percentage
Valid	20-25	4	4.8
	25-30	14	16.7
	30-35	28	33.3
	35-40	33	39.3
	above 40	5	6.0
	Total	84	100.0

Source: primary data 2017

From the above table 1 above about the Age of the respondents indicates that 4.8% (4) of the total respondents were between “20-25” years of age. While 16.7% (14) are between 25-30 years of age, and 33.3% (28) of the total respondents are between “30-35”, “39.3% (33) are between 35-40 years of age, and 6% (5) “above 42 of age.As the result of age of respondents mostly ‘30-40’ “39.3% (33).

Table 2 Gender of respondents

Gender of respondents			
		Frequency	Percentage
Valid	Male	58	69.0
	Female	26	31.0
	Total	84	100.0

Source: primary data 2017

According to the table 4.2 indicates the Gender of respondents these were 69% (58) of the total respondents were “Male” while the 31% (26) of the total respondents “Female”. So that the most respondents were male 69% (58) of the total respondent.

Table 3 Marital status

Marital status			
		Frequency	Percentage
Valid	Single	11	13.1
	Married	62	73.8
	Divorced and widowed	8	9.5
	Co habitation	3	3.6
	Total	84	100.0

Source: primary data 2017

Based on the table 4.3 shows the Marital status of the respondents and the findings were. 13.1% (11) of the total were “single”, 73.8% (62) of the total married, 9.5 % (8) of the total are divorced or widowed and 3.6 % (3) are co-habiting.

Table 4 Educational level of respondents

Educational level of respondents			
		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Secondary	5	6.0
	Bachelor degree	54	64.3
	Master degree	12	14.3
	Others	13	15.5
	Total	84	100

Source: primary data 2017

According to the table 4.4 illustrates the Education level of respondent and the findings were, 6 % (5) of the total “secondary level”, 64.3 % (54) of the total “Bachelor degree holders”, 14.3 % (12) of the total “Master degree” and 15.5% (13) of the total respondents are under “others”.

Table 5 Occupation of respondents

Occupation of respondents			
		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Politician	14	16.7
	Businessman	10	11.9
	Private employee	13	15.5
	Others	47	56.0
	Total	84	100.0

Source: primary data 2017

As indicates table 5 above the Occupation level of the respondents were 16.7% (14) were “politicians”, 11.9 % (10) were “businessman”, 15.5 % (13) of the total were “private employee “and 56% (47) of the total were under “other”.

4.2. Data presentation and analysis.

After completion data gathering process, the researchers were recorded, stored and analyzed the responses of the respondents of the questions by using SPSS version16.0 specially data was analyzed descriptive statistics. Hence the below tables presented the analysis of the questions asked to the respondents.

Table 6 Globalization has positive effect on Horn Africa countries

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Agree	16	19
	Strongly Agree	44	52.4
	Neutral	5	6
	Disagree	7	8
	strongly disagree	8	9.6
	Total	84	100.0

Source: primary data 2017

According to the above table 6 indicates that 19% of the respondents agree, 52.4% of the respondents strongly agree, 6% neutral, 8% of the respondents disagree, and 9.6% of the respondents Strongly disagree. The implication from this result is the majority of the respondents said strongly Agree. So, this indicates that the globalization has positive impact on Horn African countries.

Table 7 Globalization has negative effect on Horn African countries

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Agree	20	24
	Strongly Agree	10	11
	Neutral	4	5
	Disagree	25	30
	Strongly Disagree	25	30
	Total	84	100.0

Source: primary data 2017

Based on the above table 7 indicates that 24% of the respondents agree, 10% of the respondents strongly agree, 5 neutral, 30% of the respondents disagree, and 30% of the respondents strongly disagree. The implication from this result is the majority of the respondents said disagree and strongly disagree so the result indicates the globalization has some negative effect on horn African countries.

Table 8 Globalization effected Horn African culture

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Agree	42	50.0
	Strongly Agree	19	23.3
	Neutral	14	16.7
	Disagree	6	6.7
	strongly disagree	3	3.3
	Total	84	100.0

Source: primary data 2017

According to the above table 8 indicates that 50% of the respondents agree, 23.3% of the respondents strongly agree, 16.7 neutral, 6.7% of the respondents disagree, and 3.3% of the respondents Strongly disagree. The implication from this result is the majority of the respondents said Agree. So, this indicates that the globalization effected African culture.

Table 9 Globalization improved horn African technology

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Agree	25	30.0
	Strongly agree	48	56.7
	Neutral	3	3.3
	Disagree	8	10.0
	Total	84	100.0

Source: primary data 2017

Based on the above table 9 indicates that 30% of the respondents agree, 56.7% of the respondents strongly agree, 3.3 neutral, were 10% of the respondents disagree. The implication from this result is the majority of the respondents strongly Agree. So, this indicates that the globalization improved African technology.

Table 10 Globalization contributed Horn African conflict

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Agree	28	33.3
	Strongly agree	34	40.0
	Neutral	8	10.0
	Disagree	11	13.3
	Strongly disagree	2	3.3
	Total	84	100.0

Source: primary data 2017

The above table 10 indicates that 33.3% of the respondents agree, 40% of the respondents strongly agree, 10 neutral, 13.3% of the respondents disagree, and 3.3% of the respondents strongly disagree. The implication from this result is

the majority of the respondents said strongly Agree. So this indicates that the globalization effected Horn African countries culture.

Table 11 Globalization supported Horn African countries poverty

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Agree	25	30.0
	Strongly agree	11	13.3
	Neutral	14	16.7
	Disagree	17	20.0
	Strongly disagree	17	20.0
	Total	84	100.0

Source: primary data 2017

The above table 11 indicates that 30% of the respondents agree, 13.3% of the respondents strongly agree, 16.7 neutral, 20% of the respondents disagree, and 20% of the respondents strongly disagree. The implication from this result is the majority of the respondents said Agree. So, this indicates that the globalization supported African poverty.

Table 12 Globalization damaged Horn African borders

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Agree	22	26.7
	Strongly agree	25	30.0
	Neutral	15	16.7
	Disagree	11	13.3
	Strongly disagree	11	13.3
	Total	84	100.0

Source: primary data 2017

The above table 12 indicates that 26.7% of the respondents agree, 30% of the respondents strongly agree, 16.7 neutral, 13.3% of the respondents disagree, and 13.3% of the respondents strongly disagree. The implication from this result is the majority of the respondents said strongly Agree. So this indicates that the globalization damaged African borders.

Table 13 Globalization facilitates Horn African Education

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Agree	22	26.7
	Strongaly Agree	50	60.0
	Neutral	6	6.7
	Strongly disagree	6	6.7
	Total	84	100.0

Source: primary data 2017

The above table 13 indicates that 26.7% of the respondents agree, 60% of the respondents strongly agree, 6.7 neutral, 6.7% and 6.7% of the respondents strongly disagree. The implication from this result is the majority of the respondents said strongly Agree. So, this indicates that the globalization facilitates African education.

Table 14 Globalization improved economic growth in Horn Africa Countries

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Agree	28	33.3
	Strongly Agree	26	30.0
	Neutral	8	10.0
	Disagree	14	16.7
	Strongly disagree	8	10.0
	Total	84	100.0

Source: primary data 2017

The above table 14 indicates that 33.3% of the respondents agree, 30% of the respondents strongly agree, 10 neutral, 16.7% of the respondents disagree, and 10% of the respondents Strongly disagree. The implication from this result is the majority of the respondents said Agree. So, this indicates that the globalization improved economic growth in Horn Africa countries.

Table 15 Globalization participated political system in Horn Africa Countries

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Agree	14	16.7
	Strongly Agree	26	30.0
	Neutral	22	26.7
	Disagree	17	20.0
	Strongly disagree	5	6.7
	Total	84	100.0

Source: primary data 2017

According to the above table 15 indicates that 16.6% of the respondents agree, 30% of the respondents strongly agree, 26.7 neutral, 20% of the respondents disagree, and 6.7% of the respondents Strongly disagree. The implication from this result is the majority of the respondents said strongly Agree. So, this indicates that the globalization participated political system in Horn African Countries.

Table 16 Globalization transmitted disease killers in Horn African Countries

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Agree	14	16.7
	Strongly agree	36	43.3
	Neutral	6	6.7
	Disagree	11	13.3
	Strongly disagree	17	20.0
	Total	84	100.0

Source: primary data 2017

Based on the above table 16 indicates that 16.7% of the respondents agree, 43.3% of the respondents strongly agree, 6.7 neutral, 13.3% of the respondents disagree, and 20% of the respondents strongly disagree. The implication from this result is the majority of the respondents said strongly Agree. So, this indicates that the globalization transmitted dangerous diseases.

Table 17 High level of globalization exists on Horn Africa countries

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Agree	14	16.7
	Strongly agree	36	43.3
	Neutral	6	7.
	Disagree	15	18
	Strongly disagree	13	15
	Total	84	100.0

Source: primary data 2017

According to the table 17 above indicates that almost 60% of the respondents agree that level of globalization exist on Horn Africa countries is high while almost 35 % of respondents disagree the level of globalization exist on Horn Africa countries is high, on their hand only 7% of respondents neither agree nor disagree that the level of globalization exist on Horn Africa countries is high. Therefore, the majority of the respondents agree that the level \ of globalization exist on Horn Africa countries is high level.

Table 18 The negative effects of globalization on horn African Countries it can controlled through Making the task of poverty eradication more indigenous

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Agree	23	27
	Strongly agree	36	43.3
	Neutral	6	7.
	Disagree	15	18
	Strongly disagree	4	4.7
	Total	84	100.0

Source: primary data 2017

Based on the table 18 above indicates that almost 70.3% of the respondents agree that making the task of poverty eradication can be controlled the negative effects of globalization on horn African Countries While only 22.7 % disagree it, therefore the majority of the study indicates that poverty eradication can be controlled the negative effects of globalization on horn African Countries.

Table 19 The negative effects of globalization on horn African Countries it can controlled by Avoiding Debt accumulation and the debt burden

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Agree	19	22.7
	Strongly agree	42	50
	Neutral	3	3.5
	Disagree	10	11.9
	Strongly disagree	10	11.9
	Total	84	100.0

Source: primary data 2017

According to the table 19 above indicates that. 72.7 % of the respondents were agree that avoiding debt accumulation and debt burden can be eliminating the negative effects of globalization on horn african countries, while only 23.8 of

the respondents disagree that avoiding debt accumulation and debt burden can be eliminating the negative effects of globalization on horn african countries. As the majority of the study agree that avoiding debt accumulation and debt burden can be eliminating the negative effects of globalization on horn african countries.

Table 20 Improve the democratization process of their governments, political systems and societies it can controlled the negative effects of globalization on horn African Countries

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Agree	19	26.1
	Strongly agree	42	50
	Neutral	10	11.9
	Disagree	5	6
	Strongly disagree	5	6
	Total	84	100.0

Source: primary data 2017

According to the table 20 showed 76.1 % of the respondents indicates that Improving the democratization process of their governments, political systems and societies it can controlled the negative effects of globalization on horn African Countries , and 11.9 % neither agree nor disagree it , While only 12% of the respondents disagree that Improving the democratization process of their governments, political systems and societies it can controlled the negative effects of globalization on horn African Countries. Hence the majority of the respondents agree that Improving the democratization process of their governments, political systems and societies it can controlled the negative effects of globalization on horn African Countries.

Table 21 The negative effects of globalization on horn African Countries it can controlled concentrate through educating and empowering their people

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Agree	14	16.7
	Strongly agree	36	43.3
	Neutral	6	7.
	Disagree	15	18
	Strongly disagree	13	15
	Total	84	100.0

Source: primary data 2017

Based on the table 21 above indicates 70% of the respondents agree that the negative effects of globalization on horn African Countries can controlled concentrate through educating and empowering their people. and 7% of respondents neither agree nor disagree this statement, while only 23% of the respondents disagree that the negative effects of globalization on horn African Countries can controlled concentrate through educating and empowering their people. Thus, the majority of the study suggested that the negative effects of globalization on horn African Countries can controlled concentrate through educating and empowering their people.

Table 22 To Improve the power of the Horn African States it can controlled the negative effects of globalization on horn African Countries

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Agree	14	16.7
	Strongly Agree	26	30.0
	Neutral	22	26.7
	Disagree	17	20.0
	Strongly disagree	5	6.7
	Total	84	100.0

Source: primary data 2017

According to the table 22 above showed that 46.7% of the respondents agree that Improving the power of the Horn African States it can controlled the negative effects of globalization on horn African Countries, and 26.7% of the respondents neither agree or disagree this statement, while only 26.7% of the respondents disagree that Improving the power of the Horn African States it can controlled the negative effects of globalization on horn African Countries, thus the majority of respondents agree that the negative effects of globalization on horn African Countries can be controlled through improving the power of the Horn African States.

5. Conclusion

The summary has been organized in line with the objectives as follows

- To determine the level of globalization, exist on Horn Africa countries

Table 4.2.12 showing the level of globalization exist on Horn Africa countries almost 60% of the respondents agree that level of globalization exist on Horn Africa countries is high while almost 35 % of respondents disagree the level of globalization exist on Horn Africa countries is high, on the other hand only 7% of respondents neither agree nor disagree that the level of globalization exist on Horn Africa countries is high. Therefore, the majority of the respondents agree that the level of globalization exist on Horn Africa countries is high level.

- To Evaluate the ways in which the globalization influences on horn African countries.

From Table 4.2.1 above Globalization has positive effect on Horn Africa countries 1 indicates that 19% of the respondents agree, 52.4% of the respondents strongly agree, 6% neutral, 8% of the respondents disagree, and 9.6% of the respondents Strongly disagree. The implication from this result is the majority of the respondents said strongly Agree. So, this indicates that the globalization has positive impact on Horn African countries. as well as Table 4.2.2 above Globalization has negative effect on Horn African countries indicates that 24% of the respondents agree, 10% of the respondents strongly agree, 5 neutral, 30% of the respondents disagree, and 30% of the respondents strongly disagree. The implication from this result is the majority of the respondents said disagree and strongly disagree so the result indicates the globalization has some negative effect on horn African countries

Similarly, Table 4. 2.3 above Globalization effected Horn African cultures showed that 50% of the respondents agree, 23.3% of the respondents strongly agree, 16.7 neutral, 6.7% of the respondents disagree, and 3.3% of the respondents Strongly disagree. The implication from this result is the majority of the respondents said Agree. So, this indicates that the globalization effected African culture. While Table 4.2.4 above Globalization improved horn African technology showed that 30% of the respondents agree, 56.7% of the respondents strongly agree, 3.3 neutral, were 10% of the respondents disagree. The implication from this result is the majority of the respondents strongly Agree. So this indicates that the globalization improved African technology. as well as Table 4.2.6 above Globalization supported Horn African countries poverty that 30% of the respondents agree, 13.3% of the respondents strongly agree, 16.7 neutral, 20% of the respondents disagree, and 20% of the respondents strongly disagree. The implication from this result is the majority of the respondents said Agree. So, this indicates that the globalization supported African poverty. but Globalization damaged Horn African borders as shown Table 4.2.7 above. Finally, Table 4.2.8 above Globalization facilitates Horn African Education indicates that 26.7% of the respondents agree, 60% of the respondents strongly agree,

6.7 neutral, 6.7% and 6.7% of the respondents strongly disagree. The implication from this result is the majority of the respondents said strongly Agree. So, this indicates that the globalization facilitates African education.

In conclusion Globalization improved economic growth in Horn Africa Countries and Globalization participated political system in Horn Africa Countries as shown

Table4.2.9 -4.2.10 above. To examine the possible strategies of controlling the negative effects of globalization on horn African Countries

From Table4.2.13 up to Table4.2.17 showed the possible strategies of controlling the negative effects of globalization on horn African Countries and the findings suggested that the negative effects of globalization on horn African Countries it can controlled through Making the task of poverty eradication more indigenous since 70.3% of respondents agree this. as well as the possible strategies of controlling the negative effects of globalization on horn African Countries is Avoiding Debt accumulation and the debt burden.

Similarly, the researcher found out that improving the democratization process of their governments, political systems and societies it can controlled the negative effects of globalization on horn African Countries since 76.1 % of the respondents agree it. Furthermore, the negative effects of globalization on horn African Countries it can controlled concentrate through educating and empowering their people. Finally, the researcher found out that improving the power of the Horn African States it can controlled the negative effects of globalization on horn African Countries,

Recommendation

Finally, from this research effect of Globalization in horn African countries is discovered and analyzed, in order to help governments and international institutions to know and solve current problems of Globalization. the Possible recommendations are provided as follows:

- Conduct an in-depth assessment on effect of Globalization in Africa
- To make collaboration among Africa economically and politically.
- To make free trade among African countries
- To make specialization for each country in Africa to exchange Goods among countries and increase production.
- To belief Horn African countries can do what other people do.
- To encourage the production of Horn Africa countries.
- To get enough modern equipment to increase production of Horn Africa countries

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